

Structure Elucidation of Oligosaccharides from *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn. Seeds Glucomannan

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Upon partial acid hydrolysis, *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn. seeds glucomannan afforded mainly 4 *O*- β -D-mannopyranosyl-D-mannopyranose and *O*- β -D-glucopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)-*O*- β -D-mannopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)-*O*- β -D-mannopyranose.

In our earlier communications^{1,2}, *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn. seeds glucomannan was found to be composed of D-glucose and D-mannose in a molar ratio of 1 : 3. Methylation, periodate oxidation³ and Smith degradation studies⁴ of this glucomannan revealed that the D-glucopyranose units mostly occupy the terminal position in the main chain, which consists predominantly of D-mannopyranose units. The present communication deals mainly with the isolation and structure elucidation of oligosaccharides, obtained from the partial acid hydrolysis of the glucomannan. Chromatography⁴ of the partial acid hydrolysate over charcoal-celite column followed by paper chromatography⁵ afforded one disaccharide and one trisaccharide. Each oligosaccharide was purified and characterised by its optical rotation, formation of crystalline derivative (disaccharide only); degree of polymerisation⁶, reduction with sodium borohydride, complete acid hydrolysis and periodate oxidation. The oligosaccharides were characterised as 4-*O*- β -D-mannopyranosyl-D-mannopyranose (A) and *O*- β -D-glucopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)-*O*- β -D-mannopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)-*O*- β -D-mannopyranose (B).

Experimental

Paper chromatography was carried out by descending technique using the following solvent systems (v/v); (S_1) n-butanol-acetic acid-water (4 : 1 : 5 upper layer)⁷, (S_2) ethyl acetate-acetic acid-water (9 : 2 : 2 upper layer)⁸ and (S_3) ethyl acetate-pyridine-water (10 : 4 : 3 upper layer)⁹ and *p*-anisidine phosphate¹⁰ (R_1) as spray reagent for detecting the sugars. Unless otherwise stated, all evaporations were carried out at 40–50° under diminished pressure. The optical rotation values were recorded after equilibrium. All melting points are uncorrected. The R_{gal} and R_{glu} refer to the rate of movement of sugar relative to D-galactose and D-glucose, respectively. The sugar mixture was separated on charcoal-celite (1 : 1, w/w) columns using water, followed by 2.5, 5.0, 7.5 and 10.0% (v/v) aqueous ethanol as eluants. The eluates were further separated by paper chromatography on

Whatman no. 3 sheets using solvent system S_2 and the degree of polymerisation was determined by Timell's method⁶.

Partial acid hydrolysis: After a series of trial experiments, the following method was carried out for the partial acid hydrolysis^{11,12} to obtain the maximum yield of oligosaccharides. Pure glucomannan (20 g) was dissolved in sulphuric acid (1.5 N; 800 cm³) kept at 4–5° for 24 h and then heated on a boiling water-bath for 20 min. The hydrolysate was cooled, filtered and neutralised (barium carbonate), filtered and concentrated to a small volume (50 cm³). Ethanol (350 cm³) was then added with mechanical stirring when the degraded glucomannan was precipitated as white coarse powder, filtered and dried. Paper chromatographic examination of syrup obtained after concentration of the ethanolic extract showed the presence of D-glucose, D-mannose and a number of oligosaccharides.

Separation of oligosaccharides: Chromatographic absorption method¹³ were carried out for the separation of oligosaccharides on a charcoal-celite (1 : 1, w/w) column (64 \times 2.5 cm). The column was first eluted with water (2 dm³) under 6 lb/sq. inch pressure to remove monosaccharides and then successively with 2 dm³ each of 2.5, 5.0, 7.5 and 10.0% (v/v) aqueous ethanol. Each fraction (100 cm³) was concentrated and examined paper chromatographically (solvent S_1) and spray reagent (R_1). It was observed that each fraction was not a single component but a mixture of two or three oligosaccharides.

Appropriate fractions of the eluate were mixed together and the suspended impurities were removed by dissolving them in aqueous methanol, filtered and concentrated to a syrup. The constituent oligosaccharides were separated by Whatman no. 3 paper, using solvent system S_2 . The corresponding sugar strips were cut out and eluted with water¹⁴, and finally concentrated to syrup. It led to the isolation of one disaccharide¹⁵ and one trisaccharide¹⁵ in the pure form which were characterised as follows.

Oligosaccharide (A) : 4-O- β -D-mannopyranosyl-D-mannopyranose or mannobiose : The oligosaccharide was obtained as syrup (0.025 g) ; R_{gal} 0.63 (S_{a}) and R_{glu} 0.52 (S_{a}) ; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} - 7.4^{\circ}$ (H_2O) (lit.¹⁸ $- 7.7^{\circ}$). The degree of polymerisation was found to be 2.0, indicating it to be a disaccharide. Upon hydrolysis with sulphuric acid (1N), the hydrolysate was chromatographically examined, to show the presence of D-mannose only. The osazone derivative¹⁶ of disaccharide was prepared by the usual manner, m.p. 204–05° (lit.¹⁷ 204–06°).

The periodate oxidation was carried out with sodium metaperiodate at 4–5° in dark for 35 h ; it consumed 5.04 moles of periodate and liberated 2.92 moles of formic acid per mole of disaccharide. The periodate consumption and formic acid liberation were made at different time intervals (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PERIODATE OXIDATION OF OLIGOSACCHARIDE (A)

Time (h)	5	10	20	30	35	40
Periodate consumption of disaccharide (mol/mol)	2.40	4.52	4.98	5.02	5.04	5.04
Formic acid liberation of disaccharide (mol/mol)	1.80	2.48	2.72	2.90	2.92	2.92

Oligosaccharide (B) : O- β -D-glucopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)-O- β -D-mannopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)-O- β -D-mannopyranose : The oligosaccharide fraction (0.2 g) was dissolved in aqueous methanol (50 cm³), filtered and concentrated to a white syrup. It was purified chromatographically ; R_{gal} 0.24 (S_{a}) and R_{glu} 0.22 (S_{a}) ; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} - 7.8^{\circ}$ (H_2O) (lit.¹⁸ $- 8^{\circ}$). Upon hydrolysis with sulphuric acid (1N)¹¹ and subsequent paper chromatography of the hydrolysate indicated the presence of D-glucose and D-mannose in a molar ratio of 1 : 2 as determined by phenol–sulphuric acid method¹⁹. Degree of polymerisation was found to be 2.8, indicating the oligosaccharide to be a trisaccharide. The reduction of oligosaccharide with sodium borohydride²⁰ followed by acid hydrolysis (H_2SO_4) indicated that the D-mannopyranose residue served as its reducing end.

The trisaccharide (0.05 g) was treated with water (75 ml) and oxidised with sodium metaperiodate (0.25 M ; 15 ml) at 4–5° in dark ; it consumed 6.08 moles of periodate and liberated 3.02 moles of formic acid per mole of trisaccharide after 35 h. The controlled hydrolysis¹⁶ of oligosaccharide (B)

TABLE 2—PERIODATE OXIDATION OF OLIGOSACCHARIDE (B)

Time (h)	5	10	20	30	35	40
Periodate consumption of trisaccharide (mol/mol)	4.66	5.45	5.74	5.94	6.08	6.08
Formic acid liberation of trisaccharide (mol/mol)	2.12	2.60	2.78	2.92	3.02	3.02

indicated the presence of D-mannose and a disaccharide (4-O- β -D-glucopyranosyl-D-mannopyranose). Periodate consumption and formic acid liberation were estimated at different time intervals (Table 2).

Results and Discussion

The oligosaccharides obtained as graded hydrolysis products from *N. arbor-tristis* seed glucomannan have been characterised as 4-O- β -D-mannopyranosyl-D-mannopyranose (A) and O- β -D-glucopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)-O- β -D-mannopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)-O- β -D-mannopyranose (B) from their optical rotations, degree of polymerisation, formation of crystalline derivative, complete acid hydrolysis and periodate oxidation experiments.

Disaccharide (A) being the main fraction, clearly indicates that the main chain of the glucomannan contains D-mannopyranose units joined to other D-mannopyranose unit through (1 \rightarrow 4)- β type linkages. The isolation of trisaccharide (B) confirms the presence of (1 \rightarrow 4)- β type linkages between D-glucopyranose and D-mannopyranose units in the parent glucomannan. The earlier proposed structure of the *N. arbor-tristis* Linn. seeds glucomannan is favoured by the above results.

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References

- R. B. SINGH and V. K. JINDAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 627.
- R. B. SINGH, *Polish. J. Chem.*, in the press.
- R. B. SINGH, *Acta Oenologia Indica*, in the press.
- G. N. KOWROBANY, *Adv. Carbohydr. Chem.*, 1954, **9**, 304.
- W. W. BINKLEY, *Adv. Carbohydr. Chem.*, 1955, **10**, 55.
- T. E. TIMMEL, *Svensk Papperstidn.*, 1960, **63**, 688.
- S. M. PARTRIDGE and R. G. WESTALL, *Biochem. J.*, 1948, **42**, 288.
- M. A. ZERMYN and F. A. ISHERWOOD, *Biochem. J.*, 1949, **44**, 402.
- H. MEIER, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1960, **14**, 749.
- S. MUKHERJEE and H. C. SRIVASTAVA, *Nature (London)*, 1962, **169**, 930.
- V. M. PARIKH and J. K. N. JONES, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1966, **44**, 1631.
- E. L. HIRST and J. K. N. JONES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1659.
- R. L. WHISTLER and D. F. DURSO, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 4189.
- C. E. DENT, *Biochem. J.*, 1947, **41**, 240.
- P. ANDREWS, L. HOUGH and J. K. N. JONES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 4029.
- C. M. RAFIQUE and F. SMITH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4634.
- G. O. ASPINALL, R. B. RASHBROOK and G. KEESLER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 215.
- A. K. MUKHERJEE, D. CHOWDHURY and P. BAGCHI, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1961, **39**, 1408.
- M. DUBOIS, K. A. GILLS, J. K. HAMILTON, P. A. REBERS and F. SMITH, *Anal. Chem.*, 1956, **28**, 350.
- A. M. ABDEL, J. K. HAMILTON, R. MONTGOMERY and F. SMITH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 4970.